

The Science of Universal Categorization and Classification Through Problem-Solution Approach From the New Intelligent Design <id>

Edgar Alberto Postrado

Founder of the New Intelligent Design <id>

Discoverer of the Topic of Intelligence and Non-Intelligence

Promoter of the New Intelligent Design <id> and Biological Interrelation, BiTs

ABSTRACT

How will you answer this scientific question in science or religion? “How can you differentiate a *created X* to an *un-created X*”? Will you answer, “The *created X* is *complex* or *irreducibly complex* and the *un-created X* is *simple* or *reducibly complex*?”. Or in Biology, a difference or dividing line between an *intentionally made* biological cell to *non-intentional*? Will you answer, “*intentional* is *information-coded* while the *non-intentional* is *no-information code*”? Or in Cosmology, an *intelligently designed* Universe to *non-intelligently designed* Universe? Will you answer, “*intelligently designed* Universe is *complex*, while the opposite is *simple*”? Naturalistic science, or science in general, needs a universal boundary line (UBL) between *created* to *un-created*, *intelligent* to *non-intelligent* and *intentional* to *non-intentional*, or their synonyms, for universal categorization of all *X*, to completely explain the whole natural realms scientifically and correctly. The problem-solution approach is the answer to this scientific quest, as derived, for this paper, from the working or function of the human brain in dealing with categorization of all objects in existence. The result is that UBL is applicable to all fields of science such as Biology, Astronomy or Psychology, etc and to all questions that deals with two un-equal objects for categorization.

BODY

1. PROBLEM IN NATURALISTIC SCIENCE

Before Charles Darwin had published and shared his scientific explanation about Biological Evolution on 1859, most scientists on that time had already been accepting, as default explanation, that both the origin of life and origin of species were created or intelligently designed (intellen) by the Christian God, that is, Jesus Christ – even though scientists from this group had no scientific dividing line between “created *X*” (*X* = anything that should be scientifically categorized/classified) to “non-created *X*”. This explanation is from the Creation Camp or Religious Camp. Logical and fair scientist will surely ask, “How can we falsify the *created Xs*?”

But when Charles Darwin had explained the origin of eyes, in his famous book, “On the Origin of Species...”, he claimed that a longer period of time (millions of years) had **changed** a *simple/unperfect* eye to a *complex/perfect* eye (*X* = eye)¹, giving science a new way of categorizing two opposite scenarios. The two opposing scenarios are: *simple and unperfect* to *complex and perfect*, respectively. The conclusion from Darwin (and after him), was that, both *simple eye* and *complex eye* are in the same categorization - no differences, a newer default explanation. So, the supposed to be ***new categorization*** in science is actually, a no-categorization at all.

One of the most bizarre and controversial conclusions from Charles Darwin and supporters of the Theory of Evolution (ToE) was that the change (in all species or all living organisms) is un-intentional, uncontrolled, non-intelligence and unguided, which means, the actual scientific definition of Biological Evolution would

always be “an unguided, un-intentional, un-intelligent, non-determined or unregulated

CHAP. VI.] ORGANS OF EXTREME PERFECTION. 167

Hence it will cause him no surprise that there should be geese and frigate-birds with webbed feet, either living on the dry land or most rarely alighting on the water ; that there should be long-toed curlews living in meadows instead of in swamps ; that there should be woodpeckers where not a tree grows ; that there should be diving thrushes, and petrels with the habits of auks.

Organs of extreme perfection and complication.—To suppose that the eye, with all its inimitable contrivances for adjusting the focus to different distances, for admitting different amounts of light, and for the correction of spherical and chromatic aberration, could have been formed by natural selection, seems, I freely confess, absurd in the highest possible degree. Yet reason tells me, that if numerous gradations from a perfect and complex eye to one very imperfect and simple, each grade being useful to its possessor, can be shown to exist ; if, further, the eye does vary ever so slightly, and the variations be inherited, which is certainly the case ; and if any variation or modification in the organ be ever useful to an animal under changing conditions of life, then the difficulty of believing that a perfect and complex eye could be formed by natural selection, though insuperable by our imagina-

1. Screen shot image of the “On the Origin Of Species..” by Charles Darwin, on page 167. Underlined is mine.¹

biological change in the frequency allele, of gene variants, in a population over generations (with time).” This maybe correct if naturalistic science had already shown the differences between *unguided*, to *guided*, between *non-intentional* to *intentional*, and so on – with experiment. Logical and fair scientist will surely ask, “How can we falsify a no-classification explanation or one-sided explanation?”

On 2014, February, on the debate between Bill Nye and Ken Ham, as uploaded in the *Answer-In-Genesis* YouTube Channel titled “Bill Nye Debates Ken Ham - HD (Official)”, on the *Answer-In-Genesis* compound, Bill Nye had asked Ken Ham about this,

I'm looking for explanations of the creation of the world, as we know it, based on, what I'm going to call "science". ...things that each of us can do, akin to what we do. We're trying to outguess the characters on murder mystery shows, on crime scene investigation. Play video from 1:48:04, ²

2. Screen shot image from YouTube on the debate between "Ken Ham vs Bill Nye". ²

Basically, Bill Nye was asking Ken Ham to share the scientific world about Ken Ham's universal categorization model of *created* and *uncreated world (or biblical kinds or universe, or any X)*, for two opposite scenarios, (like the Forensic Study of any crimes on earth), based on the Bible, that is far better than Darwin's categorization method. But the camp of Bill Nye and evolutionary scientists had no universal categorization between the two extremes, that could help scientists to pinpointedly direct the source of the origins of both universe, life, species, kinds or existence. At least, the camp of Creation had already claimed and pinpointedly explained that Jesus Christ, the God Creator, is the Source of the universe, life and existence. Did Bill Nye accept that a vacuum is the pinpointedly Source of universe?

Furthermore, scientists in the old Intelligent Design (ID) camp, (especially, Michael Behe), that is being endorsed by *Discovery Institute*, had been claiming that to categorize living organisms, or biological cell, for example, science must use *irreducible complexity* (for intentionally designed cell or intellen cell) and *reducible complexity or irreducible simplicity* (for non-intentionally designed cell or naturen cell) – for Biology only. How about for Cosmology or Astronomy or the origins of universe or particle, or in manufacturing, etc? Non-applicable, useless, of course. Some scientists, like Stephen Meyer, is claiming that *information* could be used in the new scientific categorization process, in Biology only. Thus, any *X* that has a *coded information* is intelligently designed (intellen) or intentionally created (intellen). In addition, any *X* that has *no coded information* is not intelligently designed (naturen) or not intentionally created (naturen). This is from the old Intelligent Design (ID), for Biology only. Again, but how about in Physics or Cosmology or Astronomy, or in economics or business world, etc? This categorization too is useless. Not Applicable, too.³ (See some scientists that support the *Discovery Institute* and the old Intelligent Design from this link. <https://www.discovery.org/about/fellows/>)

Although our human brain can *instantly* categorize or differentiate two different objects or scenarios, or events, or shapes, etc, like the differences between rectangle to triangle, black or white, hot or cold, etc, naturalistic science has no specific ***universal*** formula/pattern or no specific derived ***universal*** system to categorize the two un-equal scenarios empirically. If you show to any normal person, a triangular and a rectangular object/shape, and ask them if they are the same shapes, (we are talking about the categorization of shapes), I think that all persons will surely answer that a triangular shape is different from a rectangular shape, showing further, that, our human brain can categorize things correctly and naturally, but our scientists could never come up with a ***universal formula/pattern*** or ***universal system*** for categorization, based on that obvious function of the brain. Thus, a universal formula or pattern or universal system for categorization is needed in naturalistic science - to settle and to answer all topics of

categorizations/classifications in all fields in science and others, especially in the topic of origins of universe, of life and of species, etc. Or for example, to categorize the differences between a good worker to a normal worker – that too requires a *universal* categorization for two opposites or un-equal X . Or for example, a categorization of a mountain, if a mountain is intellen or naturen.

2. UNIVERSAL CATEGORIZATION PATTERN (UCP) or UNIVERSAL BOUNDARY LINE (UBL)

The solution that I would like to share in this paper is to use the newly discovered universal categorization from the new Intelligent Design <id>, of *problem-solution* approach. The *problem-solution* approach is the only way to be used for categorizing two opposites. Beyond or beside this, probably there will be none. Thus, in this paper, naturalistic science must use this **Universal Categorization Pattern (UCP)** or **Universal Boundary Line (UBL)** to categorize/classify/differentiate all opposing things, events or any X s. Below is the UCP or UBL, as written in many different forms.

Intelligently designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution
 Non-intelligently designed X (naturen) = problem-solution (F1)

Or

Intentionally designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution
 Non-intentionally designed X (naturen) = problem-solution (F2)

Or

Intentionally designed X (intellen) = $X + X' + X'$
 Non-intentionally designed X (naturen) = $X + X'$ (F3)

in where X is the object or specimen to be categorized as problem, and X' as the support or feature or reinforcement for X . In addition, (probably the word *intelligence* has a different scientific meaning, but in application or practice for UBL/UCP), the word *intelligence* has a synonym words or phrases such as,

Not Naturally Designed, Unnaturally Made, Created, Smart, Intentional, Controlled, Pre-planned, Goal-Oriented, Wise, Genius, Decided, Clever, Brilliant, Bright, Superb, Marvelous, Excellent, Very Good, Handled, Regulated, Determined, Managed, Modulated, Governed, Directed, not Dumb, not Moron and not Foolish.

3. UNIVERSAL LIMITS or RANGES

As you can see at the above universal pattern, any intentionally designed X (intellen) has always two or more solutions or features. The new Intelligent Design <id>⁴ denotes it as “asymmetrical phenomenon”, a detection pattern, since intellen has always this pattern: one Problem (P) with two or more Solutions (S). Whereas, the non-intentionally designed X (nature) is always a “symmetrical phenomenon”, since it is always one Problem, one Solution only (even failing to solve the Problem is also considered a “Solution”), thus, a *symmetry*. Thus, it predicts that the two scenarios must have a numerical limits or ranges. The new Intelligent Design <id> too has an **Initial Universal Limit (IUL)** for everything in the entire realm/existence, to clarify and empirically quantify the universal scientific categorization process:

For non-intentional/non-intelligence = $0 < P < 1$as natural...(L1)

For non-intentional/Instinct = $1 < Instinct < 1.5$as natural (L2)

For intentional/intelligence = $1.5 < Iprob < 3$as intelligent (L3)

For importance = > 3as important (L4)

For failure or Over Importance = $> 3 < Failure < 1$...as natural (L5)

3.1 (L1) “For non-intentional/non-intelligence = $0 < P < 1$as natural”.

It is the same limit for Natural Probability, i.e., Probability, which has

always 99 probability of failures and 1 success. Anything that has no intelligence, no intention and no importance falls into this category. This formula/pattern fits to this limit: *Non-intelligently designed X (nature) = problem-solution*

3.2 (L2) “For non-intentional/Instinct = 1 < Instinct < 1.5.....as natural”.

This corresponds to the instinct by both humans and animals, or some natural occurrences that goes beyond the natural/normal expectations. This separates instinct to intelligence/intentional, predicting that all humans (homo sapiens) can have either instincts or intelligence but all animals have instinct only – no intelligence at all. This formula/pattern fits to this limit: *Non-intelligently designed X (nature) = problem-solution*

3.3 (L3) “For intentional/intelligence = 1.5 < Iprob < 3..... as intelligent”.

This limit is the actual limit for Intelligent Quotient (IQ). Only an agent that uses mind (like humans, homo sapiens, or God-Creator) could achieve this limit and beyond this limit. All animals have no intelligence and can never achieve this limit. This formula/pattern or equation fits to this limit: *Intelligently designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution*

3.4 (L4) “For importance = > 3.....as important.”

This limit is solely for importance of any X to survive, or exist or success. Take note that the limit of “success” here is different from “success” in L1. This formula or equation fits to this limit: *Intelligently designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution-solution-...*

3.5 (L5) “For failure or Over Importance = > 3 < Failure < 1...as natural”.

When an agent uses too much Solutions (S) and too much Importance to the Problem (P), that the many applied Solutions (S) had caused the system or object (X) to fail. This formula/pattern fits to this limit: *Non-intelligently designed X (nature) = problem-solution*

4. METHODOLOGY and DERIVATION

The first initial derivation of UCP/UBL (that I had written above) has been already conducted with a simple egg and tissue experiment. It is fully explained and detailed in one of my science books titled, “The New Intelligent Design <id> Turning The Scientific World Upside Down”⁴, as published in Amazon, as e-book. But since the discovered UBL is universal and could be explained and derived in many ways, then, anybody could share this scientific discovery in a different way. I will be using SHAPES, in a thought experiment, to derive UCP/UBL and end with the same result.

Now, in the categorization of shapes, between triangular and rectangular shapes, a human brain is speedily calculating *problem-solution* approach in categorizing two different things. Let us discuss triangle and rectangle for the derivation of the UCP/UBL.

4.1 Which is which? A Thought Experiment

4.1.1 *First Reaction.*

Whenever human’s sensory system, in this case, the human eyes, see two shapes, after closing the eyes instantly, at the same time, the brain’s *first* reaction is to always ask, “Which is triangle?” “Which is rectangle?” In this case, the brain sets it (locks on) as “The Problem, P , P corresponds to X .”

4.1.2 *Second Reaction.*

The *second* reaction of the brain is to look and search for the “inputted data” of X to that person. In this case, the inputted data are actually the accumulated information gathered by that person, in that person’s lifetime, through study, through experiences and through other means. The more the person is well versed or more knowledgeable to the topic (X), the more that person could input data and give data to the topic that is in question. Since the topic is triangle and rectangle,

the source of data is most probably, through experience – unless the person has no

5. *Shapes such as triangle, square, circle and so on. How and why the human brain can easily categorize and pinpoint a triangle to a rectangle (square)?²⁵*

experience for these two shapes. These are the definitions or features or data for

*Triangle = three sides, closed shape, one 90 degrees angle, three points,
two-sides has the same length, etc*

Rectangle = four sides, closed shape, two-sides has the same length, four 90

degrees angle, four points, etc.

In this case, the brain set these data as Solution (*S*).

4.1.3 Third Reaction.

The *third* reaction of the brain is to use the universal pattern of categorization, the UCP or UBL, to start the categorization or classification. This is where I discovered and derived this universal formula, the UCP or UBL, that I am sharing to you now. The brain does the categorization one at a time. The brain may start at the First Shape. The eye sees the First Shape and the brain uses the template of UCP or UBL to start the categorization.

Below is the universal pattern

Intentionally designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intentionally designed X (naturen) = problem-solution (F2)

But this is how the brain uses the UCP/UBL.

Intentional Triangle (intellen) = definition of triangle

Non-intentional Triangle (naturen) = definition of rectangle (F4)

If the First Shape corresponds 100% to the “Intentional Triangle (intellen)” in UCP pattern, the brain initially decides that the First Shape is, for thought experiment, let us assume “Triangle”, But since the brain has two options for considerations, and two shapes to be categorized, that is, triangle and rectangle, then, the brain will use the other template of UCP, the “Non-intentional triangle (naturen)”, see below, for falsification and confirmation.

Non-intentional Triangle (naturen) = definition of rectangle (F4b)

4.1.4 Fourth Reaction.

The *fourth* reaction of the brain is to recheck again the pattern by using the definition of rectangle, but used it in a negative way. The brain gives signal to the eye to super-impose the definition of triangle to the First Shape in the UCP/UBL. Assuming that the First Shape is Triangle, then, the definition of triangle will fit to the First Shape. Then, the brain will super-impose too the definition of rectangle to the First Shape, (but obviously the inputted data of rectangle will not fit to the First Shape, thus, negative), and confirmed that the First Shape is really a “triangle”. (Remember that the brain does it very fast, in an instant).

4.1.5 Fifth Reaction.

The *fifth* reaction of the brain is to conclude. Thus, the First Shape is “Triangle” and the Second Shape is “Rectangle”.

The brain uses this calculation, exactly to the UCP/UBL pattern.

Intentional Triangle (intellen) = Triangle(Problem) + definition of triangle (First Solution)
+ no included definition of rectangle (Second Solution) (F5)

One Problem (*P*) requires two or more Solutions (*P*), asymmetrical phenomenon, then, the Categorization is concluded/finalized – a triangle is really a triangle, based on its definition. Once the brain had concluded that the First Shape is “Triangle”, then, the brain will conclude that the other Shape is “Rectangle”.

This is basically the same approach in dealing with two opposites, generally and universally. For example, once the brain concluded that an *X* is created, therefore, the *X* is not non-created, or if the *X* is intelligently designed (intellen), therefore, *X* is not non-intelligently designed. Likewise, once the brain concluded that an *X* is created, for two explanations, therefore, the *Y* is non-created, or if the *X* is intelligently/intentionally designed (intellen), therefore, *Y* is non-intelligently/not-intentionally designed (naturen).

To the human brain, the existence of First Shape (triangle) is always intentional, since the definition fits perfectly to the shape of triangle, after superimposing two different definitions and categorizations. In addition, the features or the “solutions” for the exact definition of “triangle” as a “triangle” exist simultaneously (and not gradually) with a complete “triangle”, for if not, the brain cannot recognize and categorize a “triangle” as a “triangle”. Thus, the brain predicts that the TRIANGLE has been intentionally designed for existence as triangle, not as rectangle, further predicting that an intelligent agent, that causes a triangle to exist as a triangle, exists.

5 SCIENTIFIC DEFINITIONS OF Intelligence and Non-Intelligence

Since, it was the brain which uses and applies the calculation of categorization process, then, these will be the shortest, exact, universal, correct, scientific and naturalistic definition of **intelligence** and **non-intelligence**, therefore, all other definitions of intelligence are incorrect:

***Intelligence** = when an agent uses/applies two or more solutions to a single problem*

***Non-Intelligence** = when an agent or designer uses/applies one solution, or
least amount of solutions compared to other agents, to a single problem*

6 APPLICATIONS AND CONFIRMATIONS

This is how our scientists or any human must use the problem-solution approach of the UCP/UBL, in categorizing/classifying two scenarios. For easy categorization, all *Xs* should be subdivided into three objects:

6.1 The Obvious Objects (X).

Objects that human knew the origins or well acquainted with.

6.1.1. Application 1: Good worker versus normal worker

Although different companies and different businesses have different detailed requirements or criteria for a good worker⁶ than a normal worker, the UCP/UBL categorizes the two through this:

6. Categorizing workers with the new Intelligent Design <id> and its universal categorization pattern.⁶

Intentionally designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intentionally designed X (nature) = problem-solution (F2)

Good worker (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Normal Worker (nature) = problem-solution

Which means, a good worker (intellen worker) is always one or two steps ahead better than to a normal worker in solving many complex problems inside a company. In addition, an intellen worker could become an *important* asset worker in a company if that intellen worker could be three times or four times ahead (IUL) better to an ordinary normal worker.

6.1.2. Application 2: Does a sleepy toddler uses Intelligence or Non-intelligence or Instinct to Sleep?

The brain of a toddler⁷ is not yet fully developed, which means, its brain has only few inputted data (or none at all) on its memory. Thus, sleeping with intelligence or intention is not possible to a toddler, thus, sleeping of a toddler follows this formula from UCP/UBL:

Intentionally designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intentionally designed X (nature) = problem-solution (F2)

Intentionally *sleeping toddler* (intellen) = Not Applicable

Non-intentionally *Sleeping toddler* (nature) = sleepy (Problem) -sleeping (Solution)

Thus, in the categorization process, instinct or natural should be the answer to this phenomenon, not intelligence nor intentional, showing further that labelling “instinct” as “natural or non-intelligence” is scientifically correct. Toddler uses instinct in sleeping, and it is a natural phenomenon, an obvious conclusion.

7. *Categorizing Instinct to Intelligence, from the new Intelligent Design <id> and its universal categorization pattern. Does toddler use intelligence or instinct?'*

6.2. The Obscure Objects (X).

Objects that are very hard to be detected and yet humans deal with them directly. In addition, humans did not make/create/design them since they are already existing before humans exist.

6.2.1. Application 3: Are birds intelligent for making nests, or simply using instinct?

Since there are many biologists, who are studying the nest-making of birds⁸ without *UCP/UBL* and without knowing the actual scientific definition of intelligence, scientists mistakeably concluded that *intelligence* play a key role in building nests or some concluded that other birds are more intelligent than others.

8. *Bird making nest. Is it intelligence or instinct? Or, if a chimpanzee uses stick to get food, does the chimpanzee uses intelligence or instinct only? Categorizing two extremes from the new Intelligent Design <id>. ⁸*

IUL predicts that the capability of all same species of birds that are making nests are not the same, thus, *IUL* has an initial range of 1.0 – 1.5, since nature is malleable.

Intentionally designed *X* (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intentionally designed *X* (naturen) = problem-solution (F2)

Intentionally designed *Nest* (intellen) = Nest – Plant weeds for Future Nest

– Make Nest

Non-intentionally designed *Nest* (naturen) = Nest-Make Nest

Which means, all birds are using instinct (natural) only in making nests, since all birds do not intentionally plant weeds or trees, for future usage for nests,

or nurture/culture the seeds of the weeds/trees, for future usage.

6.2.2. Application 4: Is Life or Living organism like human, homo sapiens, intellen or naturen?

Technically and scientifically speaking, if there is no living organism, there will be no “life”. Thus, to check if “life” is intelligently designed (intellen) or not (naturen) is the same as to check if a living organism is intelligently/intentionally designed (intellen) or not. Thus, human could be a good specimen for categorization.

Intelligently designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intelligently designed X (naturen) = problem-solution (F1)

So that human could live or maintain its “life”, human must have its support systems to live. The existence of eyes, hands, feet, hands, ears, nose and heart, for example, are all supports to human to live. Thus,

Intelligently designed *human* (intellen) = human – eyes – hands – feet –
hands – ears – nose - heart

IUL predicts that if there are three Supports, then, human is intellen, but since human has supports of more than three, then, human is important intellen.

Since all living organisms are composed of biological cells⁹, then, it is predicted by the UCP/UBL through its IUL that if a biological cell is intellen, we could find three defense (support) mechanisms (or Repair Mechanism) inside the biological cell that will repair damages to DNA. UCP/UBL predicts that the Defense Mechanism or Repair Mechanism will always simultaneously exist together with biological cell. These are the reported Repair Mechanisms use by biological cell to repair the damaged DNA: *Base Excision Repair (BER)*, *Nucleotide Excision Repair (NER)*, *Mismatch Repair (MMR)*, *Interstrand cross-link repair (ICL)*, *Translesion Synthesis (TLS)*, *Single stranded break repair (SSBR)* and *Double strand break repair (DSBR)*, *the homologous recombination (HR)* and *non-homologous end joining*

(NHEJ).

9. *Image of DNA strand inside a cell. Is cell intentionally designed (intellen) or non-intentionally made (naturen)?⁹ Is life intelligently designed or not?*

Intelligently designed *X* (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intelligently designed *X* (naturen) = problem-solution (F1)

Intelligently designed *cell* (intellen) = cell – 7 repair mechanisms

Non-intelligently designed *cell* (naturen) = cell - 0 repair mechanism

Thus, it is logical and scientific to conclude that both biological cell and life are important intellen, which means, the change of the frequency allele in a given population is best explained as “a guided, intentional, intelligent, determined or regulated biological change in the frequency allele, of gene variants, in a population over generations (with time).” This is actually the actual definition of Biological

Interrelation, BiTs, as replacement for Biological Evolution, from the new Intelligent Design <id>. Biological Interrelation, BiTs, is written and discussed in detailed in one of my science books, “Biology Of Intelligent Design <id>”.¹⁰

Which means further that all living organisms are not evolving but just interrelating (or intelligently relating) to their surroundings, to the design of their anatomical structures and to the limits of their physical organs capability to live, from their populations with time. If those living organisms surpassed the controlled change, they will surely die.

But many scientists may argue that the seven Repair (7) Mechanisms were formed by biological cell gradually and not simultaneously, non-intentionally and non-intelligently, through millions of years, therefore, UCP/UBL is incorrect. Thorough scientific studies are needed to show/demonstrate that a biological cell, without intentional, could think for itself, recognize the differences between mismatch to match, recognize the difference between damaged cell to undamaged cell and the reasons why biological must protect itself for existence. Where did the biological cell get the idea of protecting itself, if a biological is not intelligently designed? Is a non-living biological cell from primordial soup better than a cell of a dead human person? If a biological cell had come from a primordial soup from ocean gradually, did the sea-water or rocks or salt or dust or lightning etc. trigger the formation of cell and its repair mechanisms?

6.3 The Operose Objects (X).

Operose objects need keen and thorough scientific study of these objects in knowing if those objects are intellen or naturen.

6.3.1 Application 5: How do science can show if Mount Rushmore is an important intellen?

Mt Rushmore¹¹, as a mountain, contained four faces of the former US presidents. These faces are features (X') to the pattern $X + X'$. X = mountain, X' =

are the known faces in history in the mountain. Even though an ordinary person does not recognize the four faces specifically, that person will surely recognize that the carved faces in the rocks are faces of humans.

Intentionally designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intentionally designed X (nature) = problem-solution (F2)

11. Mt Rushmore. Categorizing a mountain if it is intentionally made or not is impossible with present science but it would be very easy from the new Intelligent Design <id>. ¹¹

By just looking at all directions with respect to the faces, one can surely tell

or calculate that the occurrences of possibilities that those are human faces exceed more than three (3). Intelligent Design <id> predicts that if we could find three possibilities that the carved faces in the mountain are real human faces by just looking at the four faces, Intelligent Design <id> predicts and categorizes it as intellen. Since we could see directly in all directions that the four faces resemble the faces of human beings, the occurrences of possibilities that those are real human faces will surely exceed three.

Intentionally designed *mountain* (intellen) = mountain -human face at direction 1 – human face at direction 2 – human face at direction 3 – human face at direction 4 - ...

Non-intentionally mountain *X* (naturen) = mountain – face in only one direction – no human face at other locations

Then, Mount Rushmore is considered an important intellen. However, the existence of Mt Rushmore before the faces were carved is a naturen.

6.3.2. Application 6. Is the universe intellen or naturen?

Technically and scientifically speaking, since the universe is composed of particles and sub-particles, space and time, (let us call the three: whole existence) then, the question of the origin of the universe is the same as question of the origin of particles and sub-particles. The new Intelligent Design <id> explains (from “PHYSICS of Intelligent Design)¹² that the existence of the “time” of the universe began when both space and particles/sub particles exist simultaneously. If there are a time differences of existence between space and sub particles, the differences would be negligible.

UCP/UBL predicts that if the universe¹³ (or the existence of particle/sub particles) is intentional or intelligently designed (intellen), asymmetrical phenomenon must be detected. Intelligent Design <id> detects two asymmetrical phenomena for the existence of the universe or the whole existence.

13. *Image of Space, a representation of universe. Is the universe intelligently designed (intellen) or not (naturen)? If there is no intelligence in the origin of the universe, why particles must have dual nature?¹³*

6.3.2.1 Asymmetrical Phenomenon 1: The existence of the whole existence.

Intentionally designed X (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intentionally designed X (naturen) = problem-solution (F2)

Intentionally designed *whole existence* (intellen) = whole existence – whole existence-non-non-existence

Existence and Non-existence (existence/non-existence) is an obvious asymmetrical phenomenon, the symmetrical phenomenon, if there is no intention or no intelligence, is always be existence/existence and non-existence/non-existence.

6.3.2.2 Asymmetrical Phenomenon 2: The existence of the dual particle.

Particle and Wave (particle/wave) particle is an obvious asymmetrical

phenomenon, the symmetrical phenomenon, if there is no intention or no intelligence, is always be particle/particle and wave/wave.

Thus, the universe is undoubtedly intentionally designed (intellen).

Some scientists may argue that a purely natural process had made the asymmetrical phenomena with no intention. Further scientific study is needed or required if that phenomenon is probable or not.

6.4. Application 7: Intelligent Engineer versus Non-intelligent Engineer.

No civil Engineer or structural Engineer or Architect or any Designer will intentionally build any structures on the top of a sand, unless that builder is insane or stupid (non-intelligent). But even though a customer has no choice but to build the house or building on the top of the sand¹⁴, engineer or architect will surely see to it that the structure will never collapse by using a very strong foundation. Here's how to use the UCP/UBL between two un-equal engineers:

14. Image of a house built on the sand. How science can categorize two designers, smart to dumb,

intelligent to non-intelligent? How about categorizing product that is Made in Japan to Made in China?¹⁴

Intelligently designed *X* (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intelligently designed *X* (naturen) = problem-solution (F1)

Intelligently designed *house* (intellen) = problem-solution-solution

Non-intelligently designed *house* (naturen) = problem-solution

An intelligent Engineer will surely use the pattern below.

*Intelligently designed house (intellen) = house- no sand- solid rock
foundation.*

An asymmetrical phenomenon, in where a house is being built on a solid foundation, no sinking sand – two Solutions for a single Problem.

Whereas, a non-intelligent engineer will surely follow the pattern below:

Non-intelligently designed *house* (naturen) = house - sinking sand (symmetrical phenomenon)

Sound familiar? Matthew 7:24-26, The Living Bible. Jesus Christ had explained that,

²⁴ “All who listen to my instructions and follow them are wise, like a man who builds his house on solid rock. ²⁵ Though the rain comes in torrents, and the floods rise and the storm winds beat against his house, it won’t collapse, for it is built on rock.

²⁶ “But those who hear my instructions and ignore them are foolish, like a man who builds his house on sand. ²⁷ For when the rains and floods come, and storm winds beat against his house, it will fall with a mighty crash.”

It is surprisingly awesome to see that the Bible had already given humans, and science clue/hint of the UCP/UBL, as discussed by Jesus Christ, the God-Creator, but it is being ignored. I started from both scientific experiments, that is, both egg and tissue experiment and thought experiment, but ending up agreeing with the Bible.

Application 8: Who is the predicted Intelligent Agent (IA) or the Intelligent Designer (IDer) of the universe, life, existence, kinds, species and existence?

Since the new Intelligent Design <id> had concluded, through scientific explanations by using the UBL/UCP, that both the universe, existence, life, kinds and species are all intelligently designed (intellen) or intentionally made (intellen), then, the next logical question will be, “Who or which is the predicted Intelligent Agent or Intelligent Designer?”

The new Intelligent Design <id> predicts that any intelligent agent will surely leave a “seal for recognition” or “pattern of intelligence” in every ***Xs*** that a respective agent will be producing – since intelligence predicts it. For example, in a family in where both a father and a mother could cook for their children. Even though both parents could cook the same Menu or Recipe and use the same ingredients, there is always a distinction between a “taste” or “smell” cooked by a father that is too different from a mother. The “taste” or “smell” is the “seal” that separates a father’s way of cooking to a mother’s, and vice versa. Just like any carmaker will leave its company’s seal or logo to denote the origin of the product and endorse its company, the same is true with an Intelligent Agent who or which intelligently/intentionally designed (intellen), for example, the Universe. The new Intelligent Design <id> called that seal as “asymmetrical phenomenon”, a pattern for an intellen that only an Intelligent Agent could acquire and achieve. Thus, to predict the IA or IDer, it is logical to use the both the UCP/UBL and the Initial Universal Limit (IUL).

The perfect or complete limit of intelligence is 3, as described by the IUL, denoting that if there is really an Intelligent Agent (IA) who will be using intelligence so that all things should exist, then, this IA must have, at least, have two Persons that corresponds to the pattern *problem-solution (two tiers)*. In addition, the maximum three (3) Persons is needed that corresponds to *problem-solution-solution (three tiers)* and three (3), as the maximum limit for intelligence. Thus, the only specific Candidate for this Intelligent Agent (IA) is Jesus Christ¹⁵. Thus, Jesus Christ is pinpointedly predicted as the Intelligent Agent (IA) or the Intelligent Designer (IDer), since He was shown in the Bible that God has three Persons and yet, has obtained at least two Persons when He went to Earth to die on the cross to pay the penalty of sin for all humans.

15. Jesus Christ, the pinpointedly predicted Intelligent Designer or Intelligent Agent, from the new discoveries of the new Intelligent Design <id>¹⁵

By mastering this technique from the new Intelligent Design <id> about

UCP/UBL, human society could advance further toward a better living.

Thus, I report to you that our naturalistic science now has a working universal categorization process, UCP, or universal boundary line, UBL, to categorize all origin topics or anything that we would like to categorize, when two un-equal *Xs* are in questions for their differences or origins.

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